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EFFICIENCY OF IMPROVING THE IT SERVICES EXPORT

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Abstract. Export of IT services is of great importance for countries. Its development contributes to economic growth and competitiveness, and its effectiveness depends on many internal and external factors. State support mechanisms play an important role in this process. In the development of exports, financial incentives, tax incentives, infrastructure creation, personnel training, and access to global markets are considered. IT allows companies to expand export activities, create competitive services, and ensure sustainable growth in international markets. It also focuses on issues such as transparency and optimal allocation of resources, justifying its role in diversifying the economy.

Key words: IT services export, digital economy, export development, financial incentives, tax breaks, infrastructure creation, training, global markets, efficiency, transparency, competitiveness.

Annotatsiya. IT-xizmatlar eksporti mamlakatlar uchun muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'lib, uning rivojlanishi iqtisodiy o'sish va raqobatbardoshlikni oshirishga xizmat qiladi hamda uning samaradorligi ko'plab ichki va tashqi omillarga bog'liq bo'lib, davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlash mexanizmlari bu jarayonda muhim rol o'ynaydi. IT-xizmatlar eksportini rivojlantirishda moliyaviy rag'batlar, soliq imtiyozlari, infratuzilma yaratish, kadrlar tayyorlash va global bozorlarga chiqish yo'nalishlari ko'rib chiqiladi. IT kompaniyalarda eksport faoliyatini kengaytirish, raqobatbardosh xizmatlar yaratish va xalqaro bozorlarda barqaror o'sishni ta'minlash imkonini beradi hamda shaffoflik va resurslarni optimal taqsimlash kabi muammolarga e'tibor qaratish, iqtisodiyotni diversifikatsiyalashdagi rolini asoslaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: IT-xizmatlar eksporti, raqamli iqtisodiyot, eksportni rivojlantirish, moliyaviy rag'batlar, soliq imtiyozlari, infratuzilma yaratish, kadrlar tayyorlash, global bozorlar, samaradorlik, shaffoflik, raqobatbardoshlik.

Аннотация. Экспорт ИТ-услуг имеет огромное значение для стран. Его развитие способствует экономическому росту и конкурентоспособности, а его эффективность зависит от множества внутренних и внешних факторов. При этом важную роль в данном процессе играют механизмы государственной поддержки. При развитии экспорта учитываются финансовые стимулы, налоговые льготы, создание инфраструктуры, подготовка кадров и доступ к мировым рынкам. ИТ позволяют компаниям расширять экспортную деятельность, создавать конкурентоспособные услуги и обеспечивать устойчивый рост на международных рынках. Они также фокусируются на таких вопросах, как прозрачность и оптимальное распределение ресурсов, оправдывая свою роль в диверсификации экономики.

Ключевые слова: экспорт ИТ-услуг, цифровая экономика, развитие экспорта, финансовые стимулы, налоговые льготы, создание инфраструктуры, обучение, глобальные рынки, эффективность, прозрачность, конкурентоспособность.

INTRODUCTION

Against the backdrop of the rapid development of the digital economy, the export of IT services is gaining importance for countries. This sector not only stimulates economic growth but also allows for increasing national competitiveness and ensuring effective integration with global markets. At the same time, the effectiveness of the export of IT services depends on many internal and external factors, in particular the support mechanisms provided by the state, which play an important role in the sustainable development of the sector and the creation of competitive services.

Government support measures such as financial incentives, tax breaks, infrastructure development, training of skilled personnel, and assistance in entering international markets enable companies to expand their export activities, create innovative services, and ensure sustainable growth. Therefore, the strategic importance of improving government mechanisms in developing the IT services export network is significant.

It is important to analyze the effectiveness of state support mechanisms in developing the export of IT services, to identify their strategic role, and to study the problems that arise in their implementation. The results of the study will make a practical contribution to improving state policy and increasing export potential in the context of the digital economy.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The impact of the digital economy on export processes has been widely covered in foreign and domestic scientific research. In particular, P. Krugman and M. Obstfeld, in their studies, substantiate the impact of foreign trade on economic growth and emphasize the strategic importance of digital technologies in global competition. M. Porter's concept of "National Competitive Advantage" also considers digital innovations as an important factor in increasing export competitiveness [1, 2].

Local researcher Hasanov B., in his scientific work, analyzes the institutional foundations of the export system of Uzbekistan and notes that the development of logistics infrastructure serves to further increase export potential [3]. Research conducted by Yuldashev Sh. highlights the effectiveness of digital export mechanisms and the positive impact of financial and institutional support measures provided by the state. Hasanov B. also justifies the need to expand existing opportunities in the process of digitalization of logistics infrastructure.

According to the World Bank, the use of digital trade platforms in developing countries can significantly simplify export processes and reduce costs by 30–40%. In the process of preparing this article, analytical and statistical methods were used, based on official data on export indicators from the National Statistics Committee and the Chamber of Commerce and Industry. In addition, the activities of large exporting business entities were studied in practice [4].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The article used the following research methods in a comprehensive manner:

- analytical approach – systematic study of state policy and regulatory legal documents;
- statistical analysis – assessment of the dynamics of export indicators based on data from official government bodies;
- comparative method – comparing the advantages and effectiveness of traditional and digital export mechanisms;
- practical observation – direct study and generalization of the activities of exporting business entities.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The importance of state support mechanisms. The IT services export sector is an important component of the digital economy of strategic importance. Its sustainable development will not only accelerate the country's economic growth but also increase national competitiveness, strengthen innovative potential, and ensure effective integration into the global economic space. The successful operation of this sector depends on many internal and external factors, and the support mechanisms formed by the state play a decisive strategic role in the harmonious and effective functioning of these factors.

One of the main and priority areas of state support is financial incentive mechanisms. Forms of financial support, including grants, subsidies, soft loans, and tax preferences, create favorable conditions for IT companies to launch new projects, develop innovative services, and expand the range of existing services. Such financial instruments serve to increase export potential, strengthen the investment activity of companies, and expand their long-term strategic planning capabilities [5].

The second important area of state support is the formation of institutional and regulatory infrastructure. This infrastructure serves to create a favorable business environment for entities engaged in the export of IT services, reduce administrative barriers, and simplify the processes of entering foreign markets. At the same time, a regulatory framework that meets international standards will allow companies to produce high-quality and competitive services. Through a systematic and strategic approach of the state, IT companies will have the opportunity to introduce innovative solutions that meet the requirements of the global market.

The third area is related to the impact of state support mechanisms on increasing the capacity of companies and expanding export volumes. An effective support system allows for the rational use of resources, optimization of operating costs, and modernization of production and service processes. As a result, IT companies will have the ability to offer competitive services not only in the domestic market but also internationally.

At the same time, the strategic importance of state support mechanisms allows companies to reduce various economic and technological risks and ensure sustainable development. They are provided with the necessary resources to make quick and flexible decisions in the face of global economic instability, increased

First direction – efficient allocation of resources and increased transparency. Efficiently allocated resources increase the ability of companies to implement projects, effectively use budget funds, and create a stable anti-corruption mechanism. Ensuring transparency strengthens trust between companies and government agencies, ensuring fairness and consistency in the support process.

Second direction – aligning financial incentives and tax breaks with the potential of exported services. This approach will direct companies to high-potential projects, encourage the creation of innovative services, and expand investment opportunities. At the same time, aligning tax breaks will allow companies to make long-term strategic plans and increase export volumes [10].

Third direction – expanding technological infrastructure and supporting innovative startups. Modern IT parks, technology hubs, and innovation centers will help startups and companies centralize technological resources, expand research and development activities, and introduce new products and services. This will allow companies to offer services that meet global standards.

Fourth direction – training qualified personnel and ensuring their compliance with global standards. Qualified personnel increase the company's innovative and technological potential, form the ability to create services that meet the requirements of the global market, and guarantee the quality of exported services. Qualified personnel serve not only the development of technological processes but also strategic development and strengthening of competitiveness [11].

Fifth direction – development of international cooperation and integration with markets. State support serves as a strategic resource for companies to enter international markets, establish partnerships, and expand export activities. In this way, companies will have the opportunity to capture new market segments, increase export volumes, and ensure competitiveness in the global arena.

In general, these areas are an important strategic basis for increasing the effectiveness of state support mechanisms in developing the IT services export network and diversifying the digital economy.

The analysis shows that effective state support mechanisms serve as a key strategic factor in the development of the IT services export industry. These mechanisms allow companies to increase export volumes, create competitive services, and ensure sustainable development. At the same time, state support encourages companies to introduce innovative solutions, modernize technological infrastructure, and strengthen their positions in global markets.

The results of the analysis show that when implementing support mechanisms, it is necessary to pay attention to several important factors:

ensuring transparency – which strengthens trust between the state and companies and guarantees the efficient use of resources.

optimal allocation of resources – increases the capacity of companies to implement projects and directs them towards high-potential services.

focus on strategic directions – encourages companies to create innovative solutions that meet the demands of the global market in the digital economy [12].

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Improving state support mechanisms will serve not only at the company level but also to increase the digital diversification and global competitiveness of the national economy. In the long term, an effective support system will expand the global potential of the IT services export network, create opportunities for capturing new market segments, and contribute to strengthening the country's position in the digital economy.

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